

COALESCE

Co-creating the EU Competence Centre for
Science Communication

Deliverable 2.1

Science Communication Rapid Mobilisation Roadmap

Version 2.0

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1 Introduction

1.1 About the Crisis Navigator

The Crisis Navigator is designed as a strategic resource to support the rapid mobilisation of science communication in times of crisis. This second version addresses five stakeholder groups that are involved with communicating science to diverse audiences:

1. Science communication professionals
2. Non science journalists
3. Researchers
4. Civil society actors
5. Policy makers

The Crisis Navigator distinguishes four phases (pre-, imminent, actual, and post-crisis), in which science communication supports effective crisis management, creating space for constructive dialogue involving researchers and other stakeholders.

This document serves as a guide to support the different stakeholder groups to better imagine and anticipate challenges (e.g., uncertainty, ethical issues, framing). This includes careful consideration of how the identified challenges interconnect and may overlap in any given crisis situation, bearing witness to the complexity of (science and) science communication as a continuous process and acknowledging that there is no one-size-fits-all solution.

1.2 Redefining the Roadmap: From Roadmap to Navigator

The decision to rename the document from "Roadmap" to "Crisis Navigator" was intended to better reflect its purpose and functionality. The original title, "Roadmap," suggested a linear, step-by-step journey. However, in the complex and unpredictable landscape of crisis situations, a more dynamic and flexible approach is necessary. The "Crisis Navigator" is designed as a strategic resource to support the rapid mobilisation of science communication in times of crisis. Unlike a traditional roadmap, which implies a fixed path, the Crisis Navigator recognizes the fluid and evolving nature of crises.

The Crisis Navigator distinguishes four key phases—pre-crisis, imminent crisis, actual crisis, and post-crisis—where science communication plays a crucial role in effective crisis management. It allows for constructive dialogue involving researchers and other stakeholders, ensuring a comprehensive and inclusive approach. This resource enables different stakeholders to better imagine and anticipate challenges such as uncertainty, ethical issues, and framing. This emphasises the fluent, multidirectional ways of communicating needed during a crisis. The Crisis Navigator emphasises the importance of adaptability and strategic thinking, and highlights the necessity to navigate through the unpredictable crisis waves. This change underscores our commitment to providing a resource that is as dynamic and responsive as the crises it aims to address.

2 Building the Crisis Navigator

2.1 Co-creating the Crisis Navigator

The process of building the Crisis Navigator built on a co-creation methodology, grounded in stakeholder engagement and iterative development. In the first round of co-creation, the focus was on the question what crises could entail in four different areas Climate, Water, Oceans and soils, Health, and Artificial Intelligence and Digital Transformation, and what role science communicators should or could if such crises would unfold. This phase involved conducting interviews with individuals from various stakeholder groups. Researchers, crisis communication specialists, government press offices, journalists, and representatives from science culture units across the UK, Belgium, Switzerland, Slovenia, Portugal, Turkey, Spain, Italy, and the Netherlands were involved in this phase of the development. Additionally, we held four online workshops, focusing on how different stakeholders perceive crises in the four different topic areas and which underlying conflicts and tensions could emerge in times of crisis and how they would unfold. These co-creation sessions were crucial for understanding the varied perspectives on what is at stake during future crises and set the foundation for the Crisis Navigator's framework.

The second round of co-creation sessions focused on crisis communication strategies. We conducted a session with communication departments from research institutes like medical centres, crisis communication researchers, and press offices from governmental departments. This session aimed to dissect how different entities communicate during crises and distinguish between general crisis communication, risk communication and science communication.

The third co-creation phase introduced a creative dimension to our process. We organised a codesign workshop with researchers from a variety of fields, such as ethics of technology, design thinking, crisis governance and safety and security sciences, who have adopted a critical, societal and/or ethical view on crisis and responsibility. This diverse group was explicitly invited to a session aimed at out-of-the-box thinking about crisis navigation. During the session we tasked them with mapping the diverse problems that occur in communicating about science in times of crisis, and with visualising and conceptualising adaptive forms of communication, reflecting on how crises are perceived and communicated. One of the outcomes of this phase is that designing an actual roadmap would be too unidirectional, and that another structure that allows for more fluidity would be more effective.

In addition to centring participation in the creation of the Crisis Navigator, we aimed to adopt an inclusive approach for its ongoing development. During various conferences in 2024 and 2025, we piloted the initial version of the Crisis Navigator, testing its effectiveness in addressing socially impactful challenges. Feedback from these sessions were vital in further refining the Navigator's design and functionality to this second version.

2.2 Iterations for different stakeholders

This second version of the Crisis Navigator is addressing five different groups of stakeholders: non-science journalists, policymakers, civil society actors, researchers, and science communication professionals. In this document, the Crisis Navigators for the different stakeholder groups are presented as texts in the following chapters. In the remaining time of the COALESCE project, the texts will be transformed into visual digital tools and uploaded in separate documents in the [COALESCE Zenodo Community](#).

The first version of the Crisis Navigator as a visual digital tool is still available on the platform, see <https://scicomcentre.eu/crisisnavigator>.

3. Crisis Navigators

3.1 Crisis Navigator for Rapid Mobilisation of Science Communication for Science Communication Professionals

3.1.1 Introduction

The Crisis Navigator is designed as a strategic resource for diverse science communication stakeholders who must communicate science in times of crises, namely: non-science journalists, policymakers, civil society actors, researchers, and science communication professionals. The tool's design allows for ongoing adaptation to specific stakeholder groups and to emerging contexts and thematic areas (e.g., climate change, pandemics, digital transformation), and other domains where science and society intersect under conditions of uncertainty and urgency.

The present tool is targeted towards science communication professionals, who aim to communicate complex scientific information to and with policymakers, researchers, journalists and the public. They are also involved in inter-stakeholder collaborations to improve effective science communication during urgent societal needs.

This Navigator builds on one guiding question, namely: How can science communication professionals navigate their science communication when a crisis emerges? 'Navigation' should be understood broadly. When a crisis emerges, science communication professionals must not only focus on what scientific information is communicated, but also how it is approached, through which media it is shared, and who sends and receives it. Effective science communication does more than bridge science and society; it facilitates dialogue

among diverse stakeholders, translating complex knowledge while accounting for scientific uncertainty, public concerns, and institutional accountability.

The tool thus seeks to bear witness – and do justice – to the complexity of communicating about science, acknowledging that reporting is a time-sensitive and reflexive process that involves multiple strategies and formats. It acknowledges that science communication professionals play a crucial role during any crisis, as they are relied upon to provide accurate, verified facts and data. When a crisis involves complex and uncertain scientific issues, these tasks become ever more challenging, making it harder for science communication professionals to foster trust in inter-stakeholder collaboration and communicate clearly and responsibly on a topic. While numerous tools and frameworks exist for crisis and risk management, there remains a notable lack of equivalent resources tailored specifically to the needs of science communication professionals working in crisis conditions.

Rather than offering standardized guidelines (“what to do”), the Crisis Navigator functions as a sensitising tool – a conceptual or practical aid that helps communicators notice, reflect on, and interpret subtle aspects of their work, such as audience perspectives, values and emotions, or ethical tensions, especially in complex or crisis situations. Sensitizing tools help professionals ask better questions about how and why they communicate in particular ways. By outlining potential crisis challenges, dynamics and relationships, it helps science communication professionals remain attentive and prompts reflection on their own practice, without prescribing fixed solutions. Because there is no one-size-fits-all approach to communicating science, decisions and actions must rest on science communicator’s professional judgement and discretion.

Ultimately, this Crisis Navigator serves as a guide for science communication professionals to better imagine and anticipate what they are – and could be – up against when communicating science in times of crisis, empowering them to navigate their practice in a more informed and reflective manner.

This Navigator is structured around a set of recurring challenges. A challenge is understood as a recurring difficulty or point of tension that journalists commonly encounter in crisis contexts, such as information gaps and trust issues. These challenges are dynamic and fluid, and they may take on particular forms within a given crisis context. However, they unfold within the enduring conditions of complexity and uncertainty that define any crisis. These generic conditions are described in the first section.

The Navigator is also structured along the various stages of a crisis (pre-crisis, imminent, actual, and post-crisis). A temporal, stage-by-stage approach helps to clarify shifting priorities, communication needs, and stakeholder roles at each phase, enabling more targeted and effective communication and reporting, taking into account the evolving dynamics of a crisis.

Stakeholder group: Science communication professionals

With science communication professionals, we regard both the traditional and non-traditional science communicators. Traditional science communicators are those who are employed in a science communication capacity – including public engagement professionals, museum staff, institutional science writers, and public relation officers and press officers in academia, NGOs/CSOs and industry – or those involved in research who devote a considerable amount of time to science communication. Non-traditional science communicators are those who are not formally employed as science communicators, but who undertake science communication on a voluntary basis or who are supported via crowdfunding/sponsorships. This includes science YouTubers / Instagrammers / TikTokers who explain science concepts or research breakthroughs to non-specialist audiences. Also included are those who may not necessarily consider themselves as science communicators, such as those campaigning/protesting for health and environmental issues, who may primarily see themselves as activists/advocates, and those involved in citizen science activities.

3.1.2 Complexity & uncertainty

Crises are invariably marked by conditions of uncertainty and complexity. Information is often incomplete, ambiguous, or rapidly evolving, making it difficult to determine causes, consequences, or effective responses. Complexity arises from the involvement of multiple actors, systems, and interests, whose interactions can produce unpredictable dynamics. Uncertainty, in turn, is heightened by limited data availability and the contested interpretations that accompany emerging events. Together, these factors challenge established routines of communication, requiring reflexivity from all those involved.

Guiding question: What are good ways to convey the current state of knowledge and uncertainty to broader publics?

To answer this question, consider:

Models of science communication: When conveying scientific knowledge and uncertainty to broader publics, different models of science communication offer distinct strengths and limitations. Disseminate information (one-way communication) allows science communication professionals to deliver clear information rapidly. However, it often overlooks the emotional and social contexts of audiences, limiting trust-building. Establishing dialogues (two-way communication) is more likely to foster trust-building and legitimacy by allowing publics to ask questions and express their feelings and emotions, although it demands time and skilled facilitation. Participatory approaches (multi-way communication) promote shared ownership and co-creation of knowledge, yet they are complex and slow to establish. Balancing these models throughout a crisis ensures science is communicated meaningfully and effectively.

Information gaps: What are the knowns and unknowns between stakeholders? How rapidly is knowledge of the crisis evolving? Science communication professionals should identify and

monitor what information is available to whom, where and when; and what gaps exist or may arise that shape public understanding. It is essential to address these information gaps while avoiding overstating conclusions or creating a false sense of certainty; both of which can fuel misinformation and erode public trust in science. Examining how other crises have been communicated – what worked, what not, and why – can help refine strategies for conveying evolving knowledge responsibly and transparently.

Science and evidence: How complex is the science? What is the evidence? Science communication professionals should aim to integrate multiple perspectives in response to these questions to offer a balanced and comprehensive understanding of an issue, while acknowledging limitations and areas of ongoing research or debate. When stakeholders disagree with regard to the robustness of evidence or which measures are effective, communicate this transparently without implying that all views carry equal weight. By contextualizing disagreements and explaining the evolving nature of scientific understanding, audiences can appreciate both the reliability and the uncertainty inherent in science, fostering trust rather than confusion.

Voice: Who is able to influence the state of knowledge through means such as lobbying, advocacy, protest, (social) media engagement, and so on? Who is seen as credible or trustworthy? Whose voices count? Which voices deserve to be acknowledged, heard, and/or given a public platform – and which ones do not? Weigh the pros and cons of giving voice to particular stakeholders and types of knowledge in society, while remaining responsive to audience concerns and providing opportunities for collective exploration of scientific topics.

Clarity and simplicity: The communication of uncertainty and complexity requires clear and concise language that is accessible to a broad audience, and that avoids jargon and technical terms whenever possible. Ideally, this language breaks down concepts into understandable and relatable explanations, even complex and uncertain concepts.

3.1.3 Pre-crisis phase

Underlying conflicts

Guiding question: What does each stakeholder need?

An underlying conflict refers to a disagreement or conflict, often stemming from differences in values or interests among individuals or groups. Unlike overt conflicts that are openly acknowledged, underlying conflicts are less visible but still exert a significant influence on attitudes, behaviors, and interactions. By adopting inclusive, transparent, and participatory approaches that do not shy away from the question “What is at stake for whom and why?,” science communicators can help to shed light on underlying conflicts amid and among stakeholders. Science communication professionals should identify where interests diverge and where common ground might be found, allowing them to tailor messages more

effectively, support mutual understanding, and contribute to more durable, equitable solutions during and after a crisis.

Collaboration

Guiding question: How can science communication professionals facilitate constructive exchanges between concerned stakeholders?

Collaboration is vital in science communication to foster constructed exchanges between stakeholders and provide accurate, coordinated knowledge. By engaging in collaboration, science communication professionals can promote transdisciplinarity, given their role as mediators between stakeholders. Several stakeholders in COALESCE activities highlighted the need for science communication platforms, along with training and practical guidance in communication. These collaborative structures should be built as spaces where researchers, policymakers, journalists, NGOs, and industry can work together and exchange insights and rapidly share verified information. Additionally, these platforms could also be used to exchange actionable advice regarding the communication of science. These platforms should be established and fostered by science communication professionals, training stakeholders in media performance, audience engagement and bridging the gap between theory and practice. These collaborations and structures would need to be established before a crisis hits, as reactive collaborations are often too slow or fragmented to meet the demands of the crisis itself. Moreover, these platforms show great potential for trust-building between stakeholders.

Trust

Guiding question: How can science communication professionals enable, preserve, and build trust in times of crisis?

To enable, preserve, and build trust in times of crisis, science communication professionals must engage in transparent, consistent, and empathic communication across all crisis phases. However, during the imminent and actual crisis phases, there is often little time or opportunity to build it. This makes the pre- and post-crisis phases especially important for establishing and nurturing trust among stakeholders. To illustrate, several participants in COALESCE interviews stressed that if trust is lost early on, it is difficult to rebuild during the crisis, and may not return even in the post-crisis phase. Multi-way science communication approaches can help to nurture trust in the pre-crisis phase, laying the foundation for more robust science communication when a crisis unfolds.

3.1.4 Imminent crisis phase

Framing and sensemaking

Guiding question: How do different stakeholders frame and make sense of scientific information and science communication?

While framing refers to how information is presented, sensemaking concerns how individuals make sense of the information they receive. Through framing, it is possible as a sender to emphasize certain aspects of a topic while downplaying others. It is therefore essential to remain mindful when using terms such as “urgent,” “crisis,” and “issue”. Although such language can convey the gravity of a situation, it may also obscure underlying causes and risk creating either apathy or fear among publics. Science communication professionals should remain reflective of both their own framing and that of others, recognizing their potential role as mediator between stakeholders.

Framing can significantly influence how an audience perceives, understands, and reacts to scientific information; yet, this does not mean that through framing science communication professionals are able to fully control how their audiences make sense of scientific knowledge. Science communication can help different audiences to make sense of scientific information in times of crises by highlighting contradictions and inherent uncertainties, by clearly communicating the actual uncertainty to the public in an easy-to-understand way, and by connecting to different personal situations and social contexts, and by tailoring messages to cultural sensitivities. The latter comprise cultural differences, and requires that science communicators adapt messages to resonate with different audiences in ways that respect diverse cultural values and beliefs.

Ethical issues

Guiding question: How can science communication promote an ethically-sound and responsible crisis response?

Science communication can facilitate responsibility, prevent misinformation, and support collaborative responses to the challenges at hand. It allows stakeholders to assess the performance of authorities and organizations and hold them accountable for their actions. It can also promote ethical public engagement by fostering trust through transparency, enabling inclusive dialogue, empowering individuals with education, highlighting ethical considerations, addressing societal challenges, building partnerships, and embracing cultural sensitivity. An important consideration is that crises inevitably raise moral or ethical concerns and dilemmas when individuals or organizations are faced with conflicting moral principles and must make difficult decisions that have both positive and negative consequences. For instance, there may be circumstances where full transparency is not feasible or appropriate, such as when revealing certain information could jeopardize public safety or compromise ongoing investigations.

3.1.5 Actual crisis phase

Values and emotions

Guiding question: What is the role of values and emotions in science communication – and how do we engage with values and emotions productively?

Values and emotions are key to exploring and communicating the complexity of crises and urgent societal problems. Science communication professionals have the ability to interpret stakeholders' emotions and shape the tone of crisis communication. The emotions expressed by stakeholders can reveal the values at stake and help frame the communication of science that captures the human dimension of a crisis. However, it is crucial to maintain a balance between attention to emotions and attentiveness to data, facts and evidence. Above all, one cognition proves particularly vital during crises: trust. People rarely evaluate scientific information on evidence alone; they also respond to the emotional cues and relational signals communicators convey, such as empathy, honesty, and openness. Integrating two-way communication approaches during this crisis phase allows for meaningful expression of stakeholders' diverse values and emotions, fostering more inclusive and responsive dialogue.

Power

Guiding question: Who has the ability to influence, shape, and control the framing and sensemaking of stakeholders and publics?

In science communication, 'power' refers to the ability to influence, shape, or control how the scientific information is framed and how different stakeholders make sense of it. These processes involve various actors – including researchers, policymakers, media professionals, and the public – each holding varying degrees of influence and authority. Questions to consider are: What counts as valid knowledge? Who decides? Whose framing prevails? And who has access to emerging technologies, such as AI, that are reshaping science communication? Understanding and navigating these power dynamics is essential for ethical and effective communication of science that fosters informed decision-making, equity, and public trust. Science communication professionals must also distinguish between competency and authority to talk about something, recognizing that giving a platform to individuals outside their domain of expertise can undermine credibility and erode trust.

3.1.6 Post-crisis phase

Reflective practice

Guiding question: How can science communicators continuously learn from, and adapt to, crisis situations?

Once a crisis has passed its peak, it is essential that science communication professionals continue their practice, as the aftermath and long-term impacts are often just as significant as the event itself. Regular reflection on science communication across all crisis stages is

equally important. Reflective practice involves critically examining responses in specific situations, recognizing how they are shaped by existing frames of thought, emotions, assumptions and worldviews. Such reflection helps science communication professionals become aware of their own positions and assumptions, especially regarding tensions and underlying conflicts that may intensify during crises. Sustained, long-term science communication can hold both authorities and science communicators themselves accountable, empowering publics to remain informed, engaged, and better prepared for future crises. By focussing on the recovery process, science communication professionals can present a more balanced narrative: One that highlights both successes and ongoing challenges.

ABOUT COALESCE

The Coordinated Opportunities for Advanced Leadership and Engagement in Science Communication in Europe (COALESCE) project is funded by the European Commission (EC) to establish a European Competence Centre for Science Communication. The Competence Centre operates under a virtual platform, offering services, tools and resources, connected to a network of physical COALESCE hubs. The Competence Centre is being developed through consolidation of research and practice from past and ongoing research projects, including those funded under the 'Science with and for Society' (SwafS-19) programme as part of Horizon 2020, namely TRESKA, NEWSERA, PARCOS, GlobalScape, QUEST, ENJOI, CONCISE and RETHINK. The role of the Competence Centre is to further develop and mainstream science communication knowledge and to foster connections between science and society. The project has initial funding for four years (April 2023 – March 2027) but the Competence Centre is being developed to be sustainable beyond the project's duration.

3.2 Crisis Navigator for Rapid Mobilisation of Science Communication for Non-Science Journalists

3.2.1 Introduction

The Crisis Navigator is designed as a strategic resource for diverse science communication stakeholders who must communicate science in times of crises, namely: non-science journalists, policymakers, civil society actors, researchers, and science communication professionals. The tool's design allows for ongoing adaptation to specific stakeholder groups and to emerging contexts and thematic areas (e.g., climate change, pandemics, digital transformation), and other domains where science and society intersect under conditions of uncertainty and urgency.

The present tool is targeted towards non-science journalists working across all forms of media; whether in print, radio or social media. Non-science journalists are media professionals who cover a wide range of topics, rather than specializing in science, and who may be assigned to report on science-related issues during a crisis, such as a pandemic, environmental disaster, or technological accident.

This Navigator builds on one guiding question, namely: How can non-science journalists navigate their reporting on science when a crisis emerges? ‘Navigation’ should be understood broadly. Although journalism is primarily about delivering information, it is also about ensuring that such information is conveyed in a timely and appropriate manner, and it necessarily – whether deliberately or inadvertently – entails mediating between scientific uncertainty, public concern, and institutional accountability.

The tool thus seeks to bear witness – and do justice – to the complexity of communicating about science, acknowledging that reporting is a time-sensitive and reflexive process that involves multiple strategies and formats. It acknowledges that journalists play a crucial role during any crisis, as they are relied upon to provide accurate, verified facts and data. When a crisis involves complex and uncertain scientific issues, these tasks become ever more challenging, making it harder for journalists to report clearly and responsibly on a topic. While numerous tools and frameworks exist for crisis and risk management, there remains a notable lack of equivalent resources tailored specifically to the needs of non-science journalists working in crisis situations.

Rather than offering standardized guidelines or a roadmap (“what to do”), the Crisis Navigator functions as a sensitising tool – a conceptual or practical aid that helps communicators notice, reflect on, and interpret subtle aspects of their work, such as audience perspectives, values and emotions, or ethical tensions, especially in complex or crisis situations. Sensitizing tools help professionals ask better questions about how and why they communicate in particular ways. By outlining potential crisis challenges, dynamics and relationships, it helps journalists remain attentive and prompts reflection on their own practice, without prescribing fixed solutions. Because there is no one-size-fits-all approach to communicating science, decisions and actions must rest on journalists’ professional judgement and discretion.

Ultimately, this Crisis Navigator serves as a guide for journalists to better imagine and anticipate what they are – and could be – up against when reporting about science in times of crisis, empowering them to navigate their practice in a more informed and reflective manner.

This Navigator is structured around a set of recurring challenges. A challenge is understood as a recurring difficulty or point of tension that journalists commonly encounter in crisis contexts, such as information gaps and trust issues. These challenges are dynamic and fluid, and they may take on particular forms within a given crisis context. However, they unfold within the enduring conditions of complexity and uncertainty that define any crisis. These generic conditions are described in the first section.

The Navigator is also structured along the various stages of a crisis (pre-crisis, imminent, actual, and post-crisis). A temporal, stage-by-stage approach helps to clarify shifting priorities, communication needs, and stakeholder roles at each phase, enabling more targeted and effective communication and reporting, taking into account the evolving dynamics of a crisis.

Stakeholder group: Non-science journalists

Non-science journalists constitute a distinct category of professionals who play a vital role whenever a crisis unfolds, acting as intermediaries between complex events and the broader public. While they are generally well-equipped to handle current affairs and report within their areas of expertise, the more complex a crisis becomes – especially when it involves multiple dimensions of risk, uncertainty, and rapidly evolving information – the greater the challenge in providing accurate, timely, and meaningful coverage. Non-science journalists face enormous pressures: they must rapidly translate complex and uncertain information for broad audiences. In crisis situations, these challenges are often amplified, as they must also consider public perceptions, ethical responsibilities, and institutional accountability, all while contending with high stakes and evolving developments. Despite these difficulties, it remains essential for journalists to navigate these dynamics carefully and ethically, as their reporting can significantly influence public understanding, trust, and the potential for constructive outcomes during and after the crisis.

3.1.2 Complexity & uncertainty

Crises are invariably marked by conditions of uncertainty and complexity. Information is often incomplete, ambiguous, or rapidly evolving, making it difficult to determine causes, consequences, or effective responses. Complexity arises from the involvement of multiple actors, systems, and interests, whose interactions can produce unpredictable dynamics. Uncertainty, in turn, is heightened by limited data availability and the contested interpretations that accompany emerging events. Together, these factors challenge established routines of communication, requiring reflexivity from all those involved.

Guiding question: What are good ways to convey the current state of knowledge and uncertainty to broader publics?

To answer this question, consider:

Newsworthiness: There is a clear distinction between the perceived newsworthiness of crises that emerge suddenly, such as emergencies, and those that develop over the long term. A contributing factor here is that newsworthiness in mainstream media is largely driven by

public visibility; by what is immediate, dramatic, and easily captured. In the case of an emergency, journalists must prioritize both the urgency and accuracy of information to ensure publics are informed and can respond appropriately. For longer-term crises, journalists need to take a broader perspective: balancing coverage of immediate risks with attention to the wider, long-term implications, particularly as long-term recovery, and systemic lessons often remain underreported in traditional media formats.

Information gaps: What is known, and what remains unknown? How rapidly is knowledge of the crisis evolving? What are the risks and hazards involved? Identify and monitor what information is available to whom, where and when; and be alert to any gaps that exist or may emerge in understanding the situation before, during, and after reporting. It is essential to avoid overstating conclusions, exaggerating risks, or conveying a false sense of certainty, as these can contribute to the spread of misinformation, disinformation, or erosion of public trust in scientists or journalists. At the same time, journalists do not always require perfectly accurate or complete information; often, they need to convey “good enough” information – sufficiently reliable and actionable that enable audiences to make decisions and respond effectively in the moment. In crisis contexts, timeliness and clarity can outweigh completeness, as stakeholders must act under conditions of uncertainty and limited resources.

Science and evidence: How complex is the science, and what evidence supports it? Consider presenting multiple perspectives to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the issue, while acknowledging the limitations of scientific knowledge and the presence of ongoing research or debate. Journalists should verify information with reliable sources, contextualize uncertainties, and communicate findings accurately, helping the public make informed decisions. At the same time, they must balance timeliness with accuracy, providing actionable information quickly while clearly signaling what is known, unknown, or evolving.

Voice: Who is able to influence the state of knowledge through means such as lobbying, advocacy, protest, (social) media engagement? Who is perceived as credible or trustworthy, and whose voices are amplified or marginalised? Weigh the implications of giving a platform to particular stakeholders or types of knowledge, while remaining responsive to audience concerns and encouraging collective exploration of scientific topics. It is also important to avoid creating a false balance between scientific consensus and personal opinions or uncertified claims. In reporting, strict adherence to “both-sides” framing (as is often practiced in journalism) can distort public understanding by giving disproportionate visibility to marginal or unsupported claims (for example, vaccine misinformation). Rather than balance for its own sake, journalists are encouraged to practice evidentiary balance, weighing perspectives according to the robustness of their empirical and scientific grounding.

Clarity and simplicity: While clarity and conciseness are well-established principles in journalism, they are especially critical in crisis situations. The reporting of scientific uncertainty and complexity demands language that remains accessible to a broad audience, avoiding jargon and technical terms that can obscure meaning. Ideally, this language breaks down complex and uncertain concepts into understandable and relatable explanations,

preventing misunderstanding and fostering public trust. Crucially, clear language may also facilitate action, as audiences require actionable information when confronted with a crisis situation.

3.1.3 Pre-crisis

Underlying conflicts

Guiding question: What does each stakeholder need?

An underlying conflict refers to a disagreement or tension that often stems from differences in values or interests among individuals or groups. Unlike overt conflicts that are openly acknowledged, underlying conflicts are less visible but still exert a significant influence on attitudes, behaviors, and interactions. Identifying and understanding these underlying tensions before a crisis emerges is crucial, as it enables journalists to anticipate potential boiling points and provide more balanced, contextualized reporting when a crisis does unfold. By adopting inclusive and transparent approaches to reporting that do not shy away from the question “What is at stake for whom and why?”, journalists can help to shed light on underlying conflicts and contribute to more effective and durable solutions to urgent societal issues.

Collaboration

Guiding question: How can journalists facilitate constructive exchanges between concerned stakeholders?

Collaboration is vital in science journalism to foster constructed exchanges between stakeholders and ensure accurate, coordinated reporting. Working closely with experts and trusted sources not only enriches coverage but also strengthens fact-checking processes and helps prevent the spread of misinformation. Journalists can build credibility by engaging with experts whose specialisations match the issues at hand and by maintaining trusted networks across stakeholder spheres. Therefore, science journalists are key to facilitating this collaboration with due diligence by building a database of contacts with experts in various fields with whom there is a relationship of mutual trust. Such connections help reveal diverse perspectives and values at stake. Before a crisis occurs, journalists should: (1) understand their audiences’ values and emotions, (2) build relationships with experts and local sources, (3) prepare clear communication strategies, and (4) test tools and platforms to enable timely, transparent, and inclusive communication.

3.1.4 Imminent crisis phase

Framing and sensemaking

Guiding question: How do different stakeholders frame and make sense of scientific information and science reporting?

While framing refers to how information is presented, sensemaking concerns how individuals make sense of the information they receive. Through framing, journalists emphasize certain aspects of a topic while downplaying others. It is therefore essential to remain mindful when using terms such as “urgent,” “crisis,” and “issue”. Although such language can convey the gravity of a situation, it may also obscure underlying causes and risk creating either apathy or fear among publics. Journalists should remain reflective of both their own framing and that of others, recognizing their potential role as alarmists. Coverage should empower audiences by emphasizing opportunities for individual and collective action, fostering a sense of agency rather than helplessness.

Framing significantly influences how audiences perceive, understand, and respond to scientific information; however, it does not allow journalists to control how people ultimately make sense of it. Science reporting can help different audiences to make sense of scientific information in times of crises by highlighting contradictions and inherent uncertainties, and by clearly reporting about the actual uncertainty to the public in an easy-to-understand way. Moreover, by connecting to different personal situations, social contexts, and cultural sensitivities, journalists must adapt messages to resonate with different audiences in ways that respect diverse cultural values and beliefs.

Ethical issues

Guiding question: How can journalism be supportive of an ethically-sound and responsible crisis response?

Science journalism can support responsibility, help prevent misinformation, and support collaborative responses to the challenges at hand. It can help allow stakeholders to assess the performance of authorities and organizations and hold them accountable for their actions. It can also promote ethical public engagement by fostering trust through transparency, enabling inclusive reporting, empowering individuals with education, highlighting ethical considerations, addressing societal challenges, building partnerships, and embracing cultural sensitivity. An important consideration is that crises inevitably raise moral or ethical concerns and dilemmas when individuals or organizations are faced with conflicting moral principles and must make difficult decisions that have both positive and negative consequences. For instance, there may be circumstances where full transparency is not feasible or appropriate, such as when revealing certain information could jeopardize public safety or compromise ongoing investigations.

3.1.5 Actual crisis

Values and emotions

Guiding question: What is the role of values and emotions in journalism – and how can journalists engage with values and emotions productively?

Values and emotions are key to exploring and communicating the complexity of crises and urgent societal problems. Journalists are uniquely positioned to interpret public emotions and shape the tone of crisis communication. By paying attention to emotional cues, journalists can better identify which primary sources to consult and how to interpret diverse perspectives. The emotions expressed by stakeholders can reveal the values at stake and help frame reporting that captures the human dimension of a crisis. However, it is crucial to maintain a balance between attention to emotions and attentiveness to data, facts and evidence. Above all, one cognition proves particularly vital during crises: trust. People rarely evaluate scientific information on evidence alone; they also respond to the emotional cues and relational signals communicators convey, such as empathy, honesty, and openness.

Power

Guiding question: Who has the ability to influence, shape, and control framing of reports and sensemaking of stakeholders and publics?

In science journalism, ‘power’ refers to the ability to influence, shape, or control how the scientific information is framed and how different stakeholders make sense of it. These processes involve various actors – including scientists, science communicators, policymakers, media professionals, and the public – each holding varying degrees of influence and authority. Questions to consider are: What counts as valid knowledge? Who decides? Whose framing prevails? And who has access to emerging technologies, such as AI, that are reshaping journalism? Understanding and navigating these power dynamics is essential for ethical and effective reporting that fosters informed decision-making, equity, and public trust. Journalists must also distinguish between competency and authority to talk about something, recognizing that giving a platform to individuals outside their domain of expertise can undermine credibility and erode trust.

3.1.6 Post-crisis

Reflective practice

Guiding question: How can journalists continuously learn from, and adapt to, crisis situations?

Once a crisis has passed its peak, it is essential that journalists continue their coverage, as the aftermath and long-term impacts are often just as significant as the event itself. Regular reflection on science reporting across all crisis stages is equally important. Reflective practice involves critically examining responses in specific situations, recognizing how they are shaped by existing frames of thought, emotions, assumptions and worldviews. Such reflection helps journalists become aware of their own positions and assumptions, especially regarding tensions and underlying conflicts that may intensify during crises. Sustained,

long-term coverage can hold both authorities and journalists themselves accountable, empowering publics to remain informed, engaged, and better prepared for future crises. By focussing on the recovery process, journalists can present a more balanced narrative: One that highlights both successes and ongoing challenges.

Trust

Guiding question: How can journalists enable, preserve, and build trust in times of crisis?

Trust is a crucial element across all phases of a crisis. However, during the imminent and actual crisis phases, there is often little time or opportunity to build it. This makes the pre- and post-crisis phases especially important for establishing and nurturing trust among stakeholders. In times of crisis, journalism can make or break public trust. Trust in scientific information is influenced not only on facts but also by relational, social, and emotional factors. Inclusive reporting that reflects diverse perspectives and values can strengthen connections with a wide variety of publics and foster credibility. Trust can be further nurtured by acknowledging emotions and the personal impacts of a crisis, and connecting with individual stories. In the long run, relational trust grows through consistent personal and institutional interactions grounded in reliability, accountability, meaningful engagement, and transparency. Transparency in how information is gathered and verified also helps audiences identify and value reliable sources. Conversely, exploiting emotions through sensationalism or clickbait is especially harmful during crises, as it can fuel alarmism or denial, undermining effective crisis management. Journalists should likewise remain attentive about the growing circulation of misleading or AI-generated images and videos that can distort public understanding.

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ABOUT COALESCE

The Coordinated Opportunities for Advanced Leadership and Engagement in Science Communication in Europe (COALESCE) project is funded by the European Commission (EC) to establish a European Competence Centre for Science Communication. The Competence Centre operates under a virtual platform, offering services, tools and resources, connected to a network of physical COALESCE hubs. The Competence Centre is being developed through consolidation of research and practice from past and ongoing research projects, including those funded under the 'Science with and for Society' (SwafS-19) programme as part of Horizon 2020, namely TRESKA, NEWSERA, PARCOS, GlobalScape, QUEST, ENJOI, CONCISE and RETHINK. The role of the Competence Centre is to further develop and mainstream

science communication knowledge and to foster connections between science and society. The project has initial funding for four years (April 2023 – March 2027) but the Competence Centre is being developed to be sustainable beyond the project's duration.

3.3 Crisis Navigator for Rapid Mobilisation of Science Communication for Researchers

3.3.1 Introduction

The Crisis Navigator is designed as a strategic resource for diverse science communication stakeholders who must communicate science in times of crises, namely: non-science journalists, policymakers, civil society actors, researchers, and science communicators. The tool's design allows for ongoing adaptation to specific stakeholder groups and to emerging contexts and thematic areas (e.g., climate change, pandemics, digital transformation), and other domains where science and society intersect under conditions of uncertainty and urgency.

The present tool is targeted towards researchers, whether in academia or industry, who wish to publicly communicate about (their) scientific issues, work, or findings. This category also comprises higher education students and staff studying science-related degrees, or those involved in research management-related positions.

This Navigator builds on one guiding question, namely: How can researchers communicate about science when a crisis emerges? Although research is primarily concerned with generating new scientific knowledge, it is also about ensuring that such knowledge is conveyed in a precise and transparent manner despite constraints, such as time pressure.

The tool thus seeks to bear witness – and do justice – to the complexity of communicating about science, acknowledging that communicating about science is a time-sensitive and reflexive process that involves multiple strategies and formats. It highlights the crucial role of researchers, as they are relied upon to provide accurate, verified (or at least, trustworthy) information. When a crisis involves complex and uncertain scientific issues, this responsibility becomes even more demanding, making it increasingly difficult for researchers to convey information clearly, responsibly, and in context. While numerous tools and frameworks exist for crisis and risk management, there remains a notable lack of equivalent resources tailored specifically to the needs of researchers working in crisis conditions.

Rather than offering standardized guidelines (“what to do”), the Crisis Navigator functions as a sensitising tool – a conceptual or practical aid that helps communicators notice, reflect on, and interpret subtle aspects of their work, such as audience perspectives, values and emotions, or ethical tensions, especially in complex or crisis situations. Sensitizing tools help professionals ask better questions about how and why they communicate in particular ways.

By outlining potential crisis challenges, dynamics and relationships, it helps researchers remain attentive and prompts reflection on their own practice, without prescribing fixed solutions. Because there is no one-size-fits-all approach to communicating science, decisions and actions must rest on researchers' professional judgement and discretion.

Ultimately, this Crisis Navigator serves as a guide for researchers to better imagine and anticipate what they are -- and could be -- up against when reporting about science in times of crisis, empowering them to navigate their practice in a more informed and reflective manner.

This Navigator is structured around a set of recurring challenges. A challenge is understood as a recurring difficulty or point of tension that researchers commonly encounter in crisis contexts, such as time pressure and information gaps. These challenges are dynamic and fluid, and they may take on particular forms within a given crisis context. However, they unfold within the enduring conditions of complexity and uncertainty that define any crisis. These generic conditions are described in the first section.

The Navigator is also structured along the various stages of a crisis (pre-crisis, imminent, actual, and post-crisis). A temporal, stage-by-stage approach helps to clarify shifting priorities, communication needs, and stakeholder roles at each phase, enabling more targeted and effective communication and reporting, taking into account the evolving dynamics of a crisis.

Stakeholder group: researchers

Researchers represent a distinct group of professionals who play a vital role whenever a crisis unfolds. They are, as one participant conveyed in a workshop, often perceived as "those who are expected to have all the answers", serving as key providers of empirical evidence to inform decision-making among other stakeholders. Although they are generally well-trained to manage scientific uncertainty, crises place them under intensified pressure to produce evidence rapidly while navigating the uncertainties of the situation itself. Researchers face the dual challenge of delivering timely insights and maintaining public trust. Despite these difficulties, it remains essential that they communicate their science as clearly, concisely, and transparently as possible, since their messages can strongly influence public sense-making, and decisions in policymaking during and after the crisis.

3.3.2 Complexity & uncertainty

Crises are invariably marked by conditions of uncertainty and complexity. Information is often incomplete, ambiguous, or rapidly evolving, making it difficult to determine causes, consequences, or effective responses. Complexity arises from the involvement of multiple actors, systems, and interests, whose interactions can produce unpredictable dynamics. Uncertainty, in turn, is heightened by limited data availability and the contested

interpretations that accompany emerging events. Together, these factors challenge established routines of communication, requiring reflexivity from all those involved.

Guiding question: What are good ways to convey the current state of knowledge and uncertainty to broader publics?

To answer this question, consider:

Information gaps: What is known, and what remains unknown? How rapidly is knowledge of the crisis evolving? What are the risks and hazards involved? Identify and monitor what information is available to whom, where and when; and be alert to any gaps that exist or may emerge in understanding the situation before, during, and after communicating your science. It is essential to address these information gaps while avoiding overstating conclusions or creating a false sense of certainty; both of which can fuel misinformation and erode public trust in scientists or researchers. At the same time, researchers may feel pressured to appear fully informed or to protect their professional credibility. In such situations, acknowledging what is not yet known is just as important as communicating what is. Acknowledging information gaps in times of crisis can help convey the evolving nature of scientific knowledge, potentially fostering trust even amid uncertainty.

Science and evidence: How complex is the science you're communicating for the receiver, and what evidence supports it? Consider presenting nuances and multiple perspectives to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the issue, while acknowledging the limitations of scientific knowledge and the presence of ongoing research or debate. Researchers should convey their research in a way that is transparent, by clearly signaling the information gaps in a language that is understood by the public to make informed decisions.

Voice: Who is able to influence the state of knowledge through means such as lobbying, advocacy, protest, (social) media engagement? Who is perceived as credible or trustworthy, and whose voices are amplified or marginalised? Using the voice of experts could help convey rich, relevant and interesting information to the public, but do be careful with familiar or famous experts that don't have an expertise in that particular topic, as they may have not been prepared well on the topic. In other words, it is not always the best choice to use a researcher's voice directly. Researchers should try to move away from deficit thinking when communicating their science, and should remain responsive to audience concerns and encourage collective exploration of scientific topics.

Clarity and simplicity: While voicing uncertainties and conciseness are well-established principles in doing research, they are especially critical in crisis situations. The communication of scientific uncertainty and complexity demands language that remains accessible to a broad audience, avoiding jargon and technical terms that can obscure meaning. Ideally, this language breaks down complex and uncertain concepts into understandable and relatable explanations, preventing misunderstanding and fostering public

trust. Crucially, clear language may also facilitate action, as audiences require actionable information when confronted with a crisis situation.

3.3.3 Pre-crisis

Underlying conflicts

Guiding question: What does each stakeholder need?

An underlying conflict refers to a disagreement or tension that often stems from differences in values or interests among individuals or groups. Unlike overt conflicts that are openly acknowledged, underlying conflicts are less visible but still exert a significant influence on attitudes, behaviors, and interactions. Admitting that researchers are not entirely neutral – being embedded in institutions, disciplines, and funding structures – can help them better understand these dynamics and anticipate stakeholder needs when a crisis does unfold. By adopting inclusive and transparent approaches to communicating your science that do not shy away from the question “What is at stake for whom and why?”, researchers can identify where interests diverge and where common ground might be found. This awareness allows them to tailor messages more efficiently, support mutual understanding, and contribute to more durable, equitable solutions during and after a crisis.

Collaboration

Guiding question: How can researchers facilitate constructive exchanges between concerned stakeholders?

Collaboration is vital in research to foster constructed exchanges between stakeholders and provide accurate, coordinated knowledge. Multidisciplinary teamwork not only deepens understanding but also enhances fact-checking and reduces the risk of misinformation. Beyond research, collaboration should extend to the establishment of science communication platforms within and among stakeholders, promoting transdisciplinarity. Researchers involved in the COALESCE activities highlighted the need for such platforms, along with training and practical guidance in communication. These collaborative structures should be built as spaces where researchers, policymakers, journalists, NGOs, and industry can work together and exchange insights and rapidly share verified information. Additionally, these platforms could also be used to exchange actionable advice regarding the communication of science. Researchers that participated in the COALESCE activities expressed their need for practical support in media performance, audience engagement and bridging the gap between theory and practice. These collaborations and structures should be established before a crisis hits, as reactive collaborations are often too slow or fragmented to meet the demands of the crisis itself. Moreover, these platforms show great potential for trust-building between stakeholders.

Trust

Guiding question: How can researchers enable, preserve, and build trust in times of crisis?

To enable, preserve, and build trust in times of crisis, researchers must engage in transparent, consistent, and empathic communication across all crisis phases. However, during the imminent and actual crisis phases, there is often little time or opportunity to build it. This makes the pre- and post-crisis phases especially important for establishing and nurturing trust among stakeholders. To illustrate, some researchers in COALESCE interviews stressed that once trust is lost early on, it is difficult to rebuild it later during the crisis. The digital public sphere offers opportunities for researchers to engage directly with diverse audiences, promoting openness between science and society. However, this also demands that researchers act as careful moderators of their own communication in times of crisis, ensuring that scientific information that is shared online remains of quality and researchers are moving away from the deficit-based approaches. Namely, this format may be able to support dialogue and interaction, researchers often still primarily fall back to deficit thinking.

3.3.4 Imminent crisis phase

Framing and sensemaking

Guiding question: How do different stakeholders frame and make sense of scientific information and science communication?

While framing refers to how information is presented, sensemaking concerns how individuals make sense of the information they receive. Through framing, it is possible as a communicating researcher to emphasize certain aspects of a topic while downplaying others. It is therefore essential to remain mindful when using terms such as “urgent,” “crisis,” and “issue”. Although such language can convey the gravity of a situation, it may also obscure underlying causes and risk creating either apathy or fear among publics. Researchers should remain reflective of both their own framing and that of others, recognizing their potential role as providers of empirical evidence and knowledge.

Framing significantly influences how audiences perceive, understand, and respond to scientific information; however, it does not allow researchers to control how people ultimately make sense of it. Science communication can help different audiences to make sense of scientific information in times of crises by highlighting contradictions and inherent uncertainties, and by clearly communicating about the actual uncertainty to the public in an easy-to-understand way. Moreover, by connecting to different personal situations, social contexts, and cultural sensitivities, researchers must adapt messages to resonate with different audiences in ways that respect diverse cultural values and beliefs.

Ethical issues

Guiding question: How can science communication be supportive of an ethically-sound and responsible crisis response?

Science communication can support responsibility, help prevent misinformation, and support collaborative responses to the challenges at hand. It can promote ethical public engagement by fostering trust through transparency, enabling inclusive communication, empowering individuals with education, highlighting ethical considerations, addressing societal challenges, building partnerships, and embracing cultural sensitivity. An important consideration is that crises inevitably raise moral or ethical concerns and dilemmas when individuals or organizations are faced with conflicting moral principles and must make difficult decisions that have both positive and negative consequences. For instance, there may be circumstances where full transparency is not feasible or appropriate, such as when revealing certain information could jeopardize public safety or compromise ongoing investigations.

3.3.5 Actual crisis

Time pressure

Guiding question: How can researchers navigate time constraints while dealing with uncertainty of a crisis?

Recognise that time is a critical factor during crises. Under intense time constraints, researchers and other stakeholders often have to communicate findings before comprehensive evidence is available, even though a crisis leaves little room for a trial-and-error approach. This makes it especially important to be transparent about the information gaps. When working under time constraints, summarising and sharing key insights from emerging studies with peers can help ensure consistent understanding within your discipline. Clear internal communication supports clearer external communication; allowing researchers to convey up-to-date information to the public in a way that is both timely and transparent about uncertainty.

Values and emotions

Guiding question: What is the role of values and emotions in science communication – and how can researchers engage with values and emotions productively?

Values and emotions are key to exploring and communicating the complexity of crises and urgent societal problems. The emotions expressed by stakeholders can reveal the values at stake and help frame communication that captures the human dimension of a crisis. However, it is crucial to maintain a balance between attention to emotions and attentiveness to data, facts and evidence. Above all, one cognition proves particularly vital during crises: trust. People rarely evaluate scientific information on evidence alone; they also respond to the emotional cues and relational signals communicators convey, such as empathy, honesty, and openness.

Power

Guiding question: Who has the ability to influence, shape, and control framing and sense-making of stakeholders and publics?

In the context of science communication, ‘power’ refers to the ability to influence, shape, and control the framing and sensemaking of stakeholders. Researchers, science communication professionals, policymakers, journalists, and the public all hold varying degrees of influence in defining what counts as credible knowledge and whose perspectives prevail. In times of crisis, researchers often feel pressured to provide answers and make decisions that go beyond the scientific role. To counter this, shared responsibility and clearly distributed roles among stakeholders are essential to ensure accountability and responsiveness. One of the COALESCE interviewees described a triangle of shared responsibility between policymakers, citizens, and researchers; each connected through multiple layers of debate and moments of interaction. Questions to consider are: What counts as valid knowledge? Who decides? Whose framing prevails? And who has access to emerging technologies, such as AI, that are reshaping journalism? Understanding and navigating these power dynamics is essential for ethical and effective communication about science that fosters informed decision-making, equity, and public trust.

3.3.6 Post-crisis

Reflective practice

Guiding question: How can researchers continuously learn from, and adapt to, crisis situations?

Once a crisis has passed its peak, it is essential that researchers continue their communication about their science, as the aftermath and long-term impacts are often just as significant as the event itself. Regular reflection on science communication across all crisis stages is equally important. Reflective practice involves critically examining responses in specific situations, recognizing how they are shaped by existing frames of thought, emotions, assumptions and worldviews. Such reflection helps researchers become aware of their own positions and assumptions, especially regarding tensions and underlying conflicts that may intensify during crises. Sustained, long-term communication of their science can hold both authorities and researchers themselves accountable, empowering publics to remain informed, engaged, and better prepared for future crises. By focussing on the recovery process, researchers can present a more balanced narrative: One that highlights both successes and ongoing challenges.

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3.4 Crisis Navigator for Rapid Mobilisation of Science Communication for Civil Society Actors

3.4.1 Introduction

The Crisis Navigator is designed as a strategic resource for diverse science communication stakeholders who must communicate science in times of crises, namely: non-science journalists, policymakers, civil society actors, academics, and science communicators. The tool's design allows for ongoing adaptation to specific stakeholder groups and to emerging contexts and thematic areas (e.g., climate change, pandemics, digital transformation), and other domains where science and society intersect under conditions of uncertainty and urgency. Each Navigator builds on one guiding question (namely: How can science communicators contribute when a crisis emerges?), which is then adapted to the specific context of application.

This present tool is targeted towards civil society actors, including but not limited to non-governmental organizations (NGOs), citizen representatives, and advocacy groups. In this case, the guiding question is: What are crucial considerations for civil society actors who need to communicate about science during crises?

The tool seeks to bear witness – and do justice – to the complexity of communicating about science from the perspective of civil society actors, acknowledging that this is a continuous process and that there is not one best way of communicating about science in times of crisis. It acknowledges that civil society actors play a crucial role during any crisis, often operating at the intersection of science, policy, and public engagement. They interact with policy makers and science communicators to interpret complex information, balancing scientific accuracy with the need for persuasive and accessible messaging to and from those they represent.

Rather than offering standardized guidelines (“what to do”), the Crisis Navigator functions as a sensitising tool – a conceptual or practical aid that helps communicators notice, reflect on, and interpret subtle aspects of their work, such as audience perspectives, values and emotions, or ethical tensions, especially in complex or crisis situations. Sensitizing tools help professionals ask better questions about how and why they communicate in particular ways. By outlining potential crisis challenges, dynamics and relationships, it helps civil society actors remain attentive and prompts reflection on their own practice, without prescribing fixed solutions. Because there is no one-size-fits-all approach to communicating science, decisions and actions must rest on journalists’ professional judgement and discretion.

Ultimately, this Crisis Navigator serves as a guide for civil society actors to better imagine and anticipate how to communicate about science based on evidence-informed decision making in times of crisis. It is designed to help them consider what they are – and could be – up against, offering resources to navigate crisis dynamics.

This Navigator is structured around a set of recurring challenges. A challenge is understood as a recurring difficulty or point of tension that stakeholders commonly encounter in crisis contexts, such as information gaps and trust issues. These challenges are dynamic and fluid, and they may take on particular forms within a given crisis context. However, they unfold within the enduring conditions of complexity and uncertainty that define any crisis. These generic conditions are described in the first section.

The Navigator is also structured along the various stages of a crisis (pre-crisis, imminent, actual, and post-crisis). A temporal, stage-by-stage approach helps to clarify shifting priorities, communication needs, and stakeholder roles at each phase, enabling more targeted and effective communication and reporting, taking into account the evolving dynamics of a crisis.

Stakeholder group: Civil society actors

Civil society actors are individuals or groups within organizations that operate independently from a government and promote specific issues, represent certain groups or advocate for change. Their work may include fostering public participation in decision-making processes and challenging the dominance of expert-driven narratives by highlighting alternative perspectives. This involves not only translating scientific knowledge into actionable

information, but also critiquing and reframing it in ways that align with social and environmental justice goals. Their ability to engage communities, challenge dominant narratives, and advocate for policy change makes them essential during times of crisis. While addressing immediate risks and coordinating emergency responses is primarily the role of governments, NGOs and other civil society actors may instead focus on holding authorities accountable and supporting affected communities. From this perspective, the tendency of civil society actors to focus on structural causes and the publics' narratives, rather than on acute time pressures, may reflect their distinct role within crisis communication landscapes. Yet, like other stakeholders, these actors face similar challenges: time pressure, being perceived as biased or politicized (and therefore illegitimate) and operating with limited resources.

3.4.2 Complexity & uncertainty

Crises are invariably marked by conditions of uncertainty and complexity. Information is often incomplete, ambiguous, or rapidly evolving, making it difficult to determine causes, consequences, or effective responses. Complexity arises from the involvement of multiple actors, systems, and interests, whose interactions can produce unpredictable dynamics. Uncertainty, in turn, is heightened by limited data availability and the contested interpretations that accompany emerging events. Together, these factors challenge established routines of communication, requiring reflexivity from all those involved.

Guiding question: What are good ways to convey the current state of knowledge and uncertainty to broader publics?

To answer this question, consider:

Information gaps: What are the knowns and unknowns? How rapidly is knowledge of the crisis evolving? Identify and monitor what information is available to whom, where and when; and what gaps exist or may arise in understanding the situation before, during, and after communicating. When a crisis is imminent, misinformation tends to spread rapidly as uncertainty grows and people may seek explanations or reassurance. Rumors, speculation, and emotionally charged content often fill information gaps before verified facts are available. In such situations, civil society actors should communicate early, clearly, and consistently, providing verified information through trusted channels and acknowledging what is still unknown.

Science and evidence: How complex is the science? What is the evidence? Communicating different scientific perspectives and types of evidence in response to these questions can facilitate a more comprehensive understanding of the issue at hand. However, it may help to acknowledge limitations in scientific knowledge, including areas of ongoing research or debate. For instance, Expert A may disagree with Expert B on what constitutes good scientific evidence or on which measures to adopt in face of challenge X or Y. Most

importantly, engaging openly with experts, the media, and the public about these questions of expertise and evidence can help sustain trust and legitimacy, which are essential for collective action in times of crisis.

Voice: Who is able to influence the state of knowledge through means such as lobbying, advocacy, protest, (social) media engagement, and so on? Who is seen as credible or trustworthy? Whose voices count? Which voices deserve to be acknowledged, heard, and/or given a public platform – and which ones do not? Weigh the pros and cons of giving voice – and responding – to particular stakeholders and types of knowledge in society, while remaining providing opportunities for collective exploration of scientific topics. Take into account that the medium in which stakeholders operate – whether traditional news outlets, social media platforms, or institutional communication channels – shapes how problems are framed and understood. For instance, social media amplifies emotion and visibility; institutional channels tend to emphasize credibility and control.

Clarity and simplicity: The communication of uncertainty and complexity requires clear and concise language that is accessible to a broad audience, and that avoids jargon and technical terms whenever possible. Ideally, this language breaks down concepts into understandable and relatable explanations, even complex and uncertain concepts.

3.4.3 Pre-crisis

Collaboration

Guiding question: How can civil society actors facilitate constructive exchanges between concerned stakeholders?

To ensure a coordinated, efficient and effective response, collaboration is essential. Civil society actors can act as a vehicle to bring scientific knowledge to politicians, and should therefore foster trust and understanding by interacting with scientists from various fields of study, (local) governments and policy makers. By working on these collaborative efforts already during the pre-crisis phase, multi- or interdisciplinary expert networks can be established that allow rapid mobilization of expertise when needed. Multidisciplinary collaboration among diverse stakeholders can help prevent fragmented expertise from creating narrative gaps in science communication during crises. By bringing together scientists, policymakers, journalists, and practitioners, such collaboration fosters more coherent and context-sensitive messaging. Through civil society actors, emotional, cultural and experimental knowledge of represented publics can find place in this collaboration as well. However, this process is often hindered by translation barriers (e.g., differences in language, professional norms) that complicate mutual understanding and the timely exchange of information. Addressing these barriers requires deliberate coordination and trust-building practices across disciplines and sectors.

Trust

Guiding question: How can civil society actors enable, preserve, and build trust in times of crisis?

Communicating science in times of crisis as a civil society actor should be focused on building and nurturing trust. Civil society actors can build trust by creating spaces for open dialogues with affected communities, representing those whose perspectives are often overlooked. Although trust is an important theme throughout all phases of crisis, it is challenging to set up participatory activities (shown to increase trust) such as citizen dialogues during the actual crisis or imminent crisis phase. Pre-crisis efforts should therefore include participatory platforms to build and uphold mutual understanding. Through inclusion and awareness of the unique contexts of those involved, trust can be nurtured by acknowledging emotions and the impact of the crisis on personal situations. By focusing on the issues of trust and collaboration already during the pre-crisis phase, a solid foundation can be set which ensures effective science communication when a crisis hits.

3.4.4 Imminent crisis

Power

Guiding question: Who has the ability to influence, shape, and control the framing and sensemaking of stakeholders and publics?

During a crisis, rapid decision making is necessary to mobilize necessary stakeholders and processes. Due to time pressure, this often results in top-down policy approaches, limiting bottom-up decision making and ignoring valuable knowledge of stakeholders such as local residents or civil society. Therefore, in contexts where civil society actors are communicating about science before and during a crisis, awareness of power dynamics is necessary. Here, 'power' refers to the ability to influence, shape, and control the framing and sensemaking of stakeholders. Civil society actors play an essential role in addressing social or environmental inequalities and recognizing community values, and hold the ability to make sure these values are not overlooked by those with decision-making power. Questions to be considered by civil society actors: Who is involved in shaping the public discourse? Who can I reach? What knowledge is being communicated? Whose knowledge is being ignored? Understanding and navigating these power dynamics is crucial for ethical and effective communication of science that promotes informed decision-making, equity and public trust.

Values and emotions

Guiding question: What is the role of values and emotions in science communication – and how do we engage with values and emotions productively?

Values and emotions are a key to exploring and communicating the complexity of crises and urgent societal problems. On the one hand, emotions are an important source of information about the values at stake in times of crises. On the other hand, giving space to emotions and values in communication can render it more effective because it enables connecting with audiences and spurs action. By connecting with values and emotions through interaction with general publics and civil society already before a crisis hits, trust and collaboration can also be upheld during crises. In the work of civil society actors, more specifically, connecting to values and emotions plays an important role in advocating for change. It is these actors that can guarantee involvement underrepresented groups or issues in science communication practices and decision making during crises.

3.4.5 Actual crisis

Ethical issues

Guiding question: How can civil society actors promote an ethically-sound and responsible crisis response?

Communicating about science can facilitate responsibility, prevent misinformation, and support collaborative responses to the challenges at hand. It allows various stakeholders (crisis responders, journalists, scientists, citizens, etc.) to assess the performance of authorities and organizations and hold them accountable for their actions. Accountability and transparency build trust, and may promote ethical public engagement, enabling inclusive dialogue, empowering individuals with education, highlighting ethical considerations, addressing societal challenges, building partnerships, and embracing cultural sensitivity. An important consideration is that crises inevitably raise moral or ethical concerns and dilemmas when individuals or organizations are faced with conflicting moral principles and must make difficult decisions that have both positive and negative consequences. For instance, there may be circumstances where full transparency is not feasible or appropriate, such as when revealing certain information could jeopardize public safety or compromise ongoing investigations.

Framing and sensemaking

Guiding question: How do different stakeholders frame and make sense of scientific information and science communication?

Whereas framing refers to the way information is presented, sensemaking is about how individuals make sense of the information they receive. With framing, senders of information structure information to highlight certain aspects of a topic while downplaying others. It is important to be mindful and reflective when using terms such as “urgent,” “crisis,” and “issue”. Whereas these terms help to emphasize the exceptionality of a situation, they may

remove from view that some problems could have been avoided or that a situation is the result of political neglect of a structural issue or a bigger problem.

Framing can significantly influence how an audience perceives, understands, and reacts to scientific information. Through storytelling, value-based messaging and a narrative that includes public values and interests, civil society actors can connect scientific topics to people's lived experiences. Yet, this does not mean that through framing civil society actors are able to fully control how their audiences make sense of scientific knowledge. The ways in which science is communicated can help different audiences to make sense of scientific information in times of crises by highlighting contradictions and inherent uncertainties, by clearly communicating the actual uncertainty to the public in an easy-to-understand way, and by connecting to different personal situations and social contexts, and by tailoring messages to cultural sensitivities. The latter comprise cultural differences, and requires that policy makers adapt messages to resonate with different audiences in ways that respect diverse cultural values and beliefs.

3.4.6 Post-crisis

Reflective practice

Guiding question: How can civil society actors continuously learn from, and adapt to, crisis situations?

It is helpful for civil society actors to regularly self-reflect on their science communication activities during any of the crisis stages. Whether this entails advocating for overlooked minorities or issues during a crisis, or involving certain publics pre-crisis to build trust, every science communication activity is one to reflect on and learn from. Reflective practice means adopting a critical and reflective stance to responses in specific situations, and to understand how these responses are shaped by frames of thought, emotions, assumptions and worldviews. This can help to become sensitive to one's own position and assumptions when it comes to tensions and underlying conflicts that may be exacerbated in times of crises. Insights gained from this reflection can help strengthen strategies in future crises.

Trust & collaborations

Similar to the pre-crisis phase, it is essential to build both trust and collaboration during the post-crisis phase; and it is crucial to repair and restore trust where it was lost or damaged. This is probably the best way to ensure rapid mobilization and effective science communication during possible future crises. It is helpful here to compare and contrast communication approaches in other crisis contexts, paying attention not only to visible manifestations of a communication crisis (e.g., misinformation, disinformation), but also to structural factors (e.g., inequitable access to information, exclusion of marginalized voices

from crisis decisionmaking) and cultural factors (e.g., symbolic framings, such as “ignorant publics”) that may or may not be used to justify structural exclusions.

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3.5 Crisis Navigator for Rapid Mobilisation of Science Communication for Policymakers

3.5.1 Introduction

The Crisis Navigator is designed as a strategic resource for diverse science communication stakeholders who must communicate science in times of crises, namely: non-science journalists, policymakers, civil society actors, researchers, and science communication professionals. The tool's design allows for ongoing adaptation to specific stakeholder groups and to emerging contexts and thematic areas (e.g., climate change, pandemics, digital transformation), and other domains where science and society intersect under conditions of uncertainty and urgency.

The present tool is targeted towards policymakers within governmental or regulatory institutions who are responsible for developing, implementing, and evaluating crisis responses and policies that shape public action. In this case, the guiding question is: What are crucial considerations for policymakers who need to communicate about science when a crisis emerges?

The tool seeks to bear witness – and do justice – to the complexity of communicating about science from a policy perspective, acknowledging that this is a continuous process and that there is not one best way of communicating about science and science policies in times of crisis. It acknowledges that policymakers play a crucial role during any crisis, as they rely on scientific evidence, expert advice, and public input to craft – and communicate – informed decisions under conditions of uncertainty and urgency. They interact with science communicators and journalists to interpret complex information, weigh risks, and communicate evidence-informed decisions to stakeholders and the broader public.

Rather than offering standardized guidelines (“what to do”), the Crisis Navigator functions as a sensitising tool – a conceptual or practical aid that helps communicators (policymakers and others) notice, reflect on, and interpret subtle aspects of their work, such as audience perspectives, values and emotions, or ethical tensions, especially in complex or crisis situations. Sensitizing tools help professionals ask better questions about how and why they communicate in particular ways. By outlining potential crisis challenges, dynamics and relationships, it helps policymakers remain attentive and prompts reflection on their own practice, without prescribing fixed solutions. Because there is no one-size-fits-all approach to communicating science, decisions and actions must rest on policymakers’ professional judgement and discretion.

Ultimately, this Crisis Navigator serves as a guide for policymakers to better imagine and anticipate how to communicate about science based on evidence-informed decision making in times of crisis. It is designed to help them consider what they are – and could be – up against, offering resources to navigate crisis dynamics.

This Navigator is structured around a set of recurring challenges. A challenge is understood as a recurring difficulty or point of tension that stakeholders commonly encounter in crisis contexts, such as information gaps and trust issues. These challenges are dynamic and fluid, and they may take on particular forms within a given crisis context. However, they unfold within the enduring conditions of complexity and uncertainty that define any crisis. These generic conditions are described in the first section.

The Navigator is also structured along the various stages of a crisis (pre-crisis, imminent, actual, and post-crisis). A temporal, stage-by-stage approach helps to clarify shifting priorities, communication needs, and stakeholder roles at each phase, enabling more targeted and effective communication and reporting, taking into account the evolving dynamics of a crisis.

Stakeholder group: Policymakers

Policymakers are individuals or groups within government or regulatory bodies at local, regional, national, or international levels who make decisions that guide public action. In crises, they must interpret complex scientific information, balance competing risks, and communicate decisions under uncertainty and public scrutiny. In doing so, they also act as science communicators, translating technical evidence into accessible guidance, framing risks for the public, and signaling the rationale behind policy choices. The many challenges they face include time pressure, incomplete or evolving evidence, conflicting stakeholder interests, and the need to maintain public trust while ensuring effective crisis management.

3.5.2 Complexity & uncertainty

Crises are invariably marked by conditions of uncertainty and complexity. Information is often incomplete, ambiguous, or rapidly evolving, making it difficult to determine causes, consequences, or effective responses. Complexity arises from the involvement of multiple actors, systems, and interests, whose interactions can produce unpredictable dynamics. Uncertainty, in turn, is heightened by limited data availability and the contested interpretations that accompany emerging events. Together, these factors challenge established routines of communication, requiring reflexivity from all those involved.

Guiding question: What are good ways to convey the current state of knowledge and uncertainty to broader publics?

To answer this question, consider:

Information gaps: What are the knowns and unknowns? How rapidly is knowledge of the crisis evolving? Identify and monitor what information is available to whom, where and when; and what gaps exist or may arise in understanding the situation before, during, and after

communicating. When a crisis is imminent, misinformation tends to spread rapidly as uncertainty grows and people may seek explanations or reassurance. Rumors, speculation, and emotionally charged content often fill information gaps before verified facts are available. In such situations, policymakers should communicate early, clearly, and consistently, providing verified information through trusted channels and acknowledging what is still unknown.

Science and evidence: How complex is the science? What is the evidence? Communicating different scientific perspectives and types of evidence in response to these questions can facilitate a more comprehensive understanding of the issue at hand. However, it may help to acknowledge limitations in scientific knowledge, including areas of ongoing research or debate. For instance, Expert A may disagree with Expert B on what constitutes good scientific evidence or on which measures to adopt in face of challenge X or Y. Most importantly, engaging openly with experts, the media, and the public about these questions of expertise and evidence can help sustain trust and legitimacy, which are essential for collective action in times of crisis.

Voice: Who is able to influence the state of knowledge through means such as lobbying, advocacy, protest, (social) media engagement, and so on? Who is seen as credible or trustworthy? Whose voices count? Which voices deserve to be acknowledged, heard, and/or given a public platform – and which ones do not? Weigh the pros and cons of giving voice – and responding – to particular stakeholders and types of knowledge in society, while remaining providing opportunities for collective exploration of scientific topics. Take into account that the medium in which stakeholders operate – whether traditional news outlets, social media platforms, or institutional communication channels – shapes how problems are framed and understood. For instance, social media amplifies emotion and visibility; institutional channels tend to emphasize credibility and control.

Clarity and simplicity: The communication of uncertainty and complexity requires clear and concise language that is accessible to a broad audience, and that avoids jargon and technical terms whenever possible. Ideally, this language breaks down concepts into understandable and relatable explanations, even complex and uncertain concepts.

3.5.3 Pre-crisis

Underlying conflicts

Guiding question: What does each stakeholder need?

An underlying conflict refers to a disagreement or conflict, often stemming from differences in values or interests among individuals or groups. Unlike overt conflicts that are openly acknowledged, underlying conflicts are less visible but still exert a significant influence on attitudes, behaviors, and interactions. By adopting inclusive, transparent, and participatory

approaches that do not shy away from the question “What is at stake for whom and why?” policymakers who need to communicate about science can help to shed light on underlying conflicts, and generate more effective and sustainable solutions to urgent societal issues. Policymakers can address underlying conflicts by acknowledging divergent values and interests early on, rather than treating disagreement as mere misinformation or resistance. This involves creating inclusive and transparent deliberation spaces where affected groups can voice concerns and contribute to decisionmaking.

Ethical issues

Guiding question: How can policy makers promote an ethically-sound and responsible crisis response?

Communicating about science can facilitate responsibility, prevent misinformation, and support collaborative responses to the challenges at hand. It allows various stakeholders (crisis responders, journalists, scientists, citizens, etc.) to assess the performance of authorities and organizations and hold them accountable for their actions. Accountability and transparency build trust, and may promote ethical public engagement, enabling inclusive dialogue, empowering individuals with education, highlighting ethical considerations, addressing societal challenges, building partnerships, and embracing cultural sensitivity. An important consideration is that crises inevitably raise moral or ethical concerns and dilemmas when individuals or organizations are faced with conflicting moral principles and must make difficult decisions that have both positive and negative consequences. For instance, there may be circumstances where full transparency is not feasible or appropriate, such as when revealing certain information could jeopardize public safety or compromise ongoing investigations.

Collaboration

Guiding question: How can policy makers facilitate constructive exchanges between concerned stakeholders?

To ensure a coordinated, efficient and effective response, collaboration is essential. Policy makers who communicate about science are key to facilitating this collaboration by ensuring clear, consistent and credible communication, fostering trust and understanding. By involving scientists from various related fields of study, (local) governments, civil society and other relevant parties (such as first responders or NGOs) already during the pre-crisis phase, multi- or interdisciplinary expert networks can be established that allow rapid mobilization of expertise when needed. Multidisciplinary collaboration among diverse stakeholders can help prevent fragmented expertise from creating narrative gaps in science communication during crises. By bringing together scientists, policymakers, journalists, and practitioners, such collaboration fosters more coherent and context-sensitive messaging. However, this process is often hindered by translation barriers (e.g., differences in language, professional norms) that complicate mutual understanding and the timely exchange of information. Addressing these barriers requires deliberate coordination and trust-building practices across

disciplines and sectors. Great care should be taken to assign responsibilities within these collaborations, ensuring that communication efforts are also aligned.

Trust

Guiding question: How can policy makers enable, preserve, and build trust in times of crisis?

Communicating science in times of crisis as a policy maker should be focused on building and nurturing trust. Although trust is an important theme throughout all phases of crisis, it is challenging to set up participatory activities (shown to increase trust) such as citizen dialogues during the actual crisis or imminent crisis phase. Pre-crisis efforts should therefore include participatory platforms to build and uphold mutual understanding. This should not only entail interaction between policy makers and the general public, but also requires sustained engagement between policy makers, scientists and (local) government. Within participatory activities, policy makers should focus on transparency and inclusion. While maintaining public trust through transparency about uncertainty and preserving institutional or personal credibility can be a balancing act, crises in the past have shown that a lack of transparency can backfire (Irwin 2021; Wynne 2006). Through inclusion and awareness of the unique contexts of those involved, trust can be nurtured by acknowledging emotions and the impact of the crisis on personal situations. By focusing on the issues of (relational) trust and collaboration already during the pre-crisis phase, a solid foundation can be set which ensures effective science communication when a crisis hits.

3.5.4 Imminent Crisis

Framing and sensemaking

Guiding question: How do different stakeholders frame and make sense of scientific information and science communication?

Whereas framing refers to the way information is presented, sensemaking is about how individuals make sense of the information they receive. With framing, senders of information structure information to highlight certain aspects of a topic while downplaying others. It is important to be mindful and reflective when using terms such as “urgent,” “crisis,” and “issue”. Whereas these terms help to emphasize the exceptionality of a situation, they may remove from view that some problems could have been avoided or that a situation is the result of political neglect of a structural issue or a bigger problem.

Framing can significantly influence how an audience perceives, understands, and reacts to scientific information; yet, this does not mean that through framing policy makers are able to fully control how their audiences make sense of scientific knowledge. The ways in which science is communicated can help different audiences to make sense of scientific information in times of crises by highlighting contradictions and inherent uncertainties, by clearly communicating the actual uncertainty to the public in an easy-to-understand way,

and by connecting to different personal situations and social contexts, and by tailoring messages to cultural sensitivities. The latter comprise cultural differences, and requires that policy makers adapt messages to resonate with different audiences in ways that respect diverse cultural values and beliefs.

3.5.5 Actual Crisis

Values and emotions

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Power

Guiding question: Who has the ability to influence, shape, and control the framing and sensemaking of stakeholders and publics?

During a crisis, rapid decision making is necessary to mobilize necessary stakeholders and processes. Due to time pressure, this often results in top-down policy approaches, limiting bottom-up decision making and ignoring valuable knowledge of stakeholders such as local residents or civil society. Therefore, in contexts where policy makers need to communicate about science during a crisis, awareness of power dynamics is necessary. Here, 'power' refers to the ability to influence, shape, and control the framing and sensemaking of stakeholders. Questions to be considered by policy makers are: What power and/or responsibility do I hold? Who is involved in shaping the public discourse? What knowledge is being communicated? Whose knowledge is being ignored? Understanding and navigating these power dynamics is crucial for ethical and effective communication of science in policy contexts that promotes informed decision-making, equity and public trust.

3.5.6 Post-crisis

Reflective practice

Guiding question: How can policy makers continuously learn from, and adapt to, crisis situations?

It is helpful for policymakers to regularly self-reflect on their science communication activities during any of the crisis stages. Whether this entails translating scientific findings to ensure rapid decision-making during a crisis, or involving civil societies pre-crisis to build trust, every science communication activity is one to reflect on and learn from. Reflective practice means adopting a critical and reflective stance to responses in specific situations, and to understand how these responses are shaped by frames of thought, emotions, assumptions and worldviews. This can help to become sensitive to one's own position and assumptions when it comes to tensions and underlying conflicts that may be exacerbated in times of crises. Insights gained from this reflection can help strengthen strategies in future crises.

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